

**A SIMULATION OF FIBRE PACKING
IN FLOW-PROCESSED COMPOSITES**

K.E. Evans

and

M.D. Ferrar
Department of Materials Science and Engineering,
University of Liverpool,
P.O. Box 147,
Liverpool L69 3BX,
U.K.

ABSTRACT

To predict the mechanical properties of flow-processed short-fibre composite components knowledge of the final micro-mechanical configuration is required. A computer programme is described which models the packing and flow of high volume fraction composites where fibre-fibre interactions dominate. The model provides information on the inter-relationships between fibre orientation, fibre length distribution, achievable packing fraction and flow history. Such a programme can provide the basis for a predictive tool to relate the design stage to the ultimate mechanical properties of a short-fibre component.

INTRODUCTION

To predict the mechanical properties of a complex fibre-reinforced composite component, at the design stage, knowledge of how the composite material will configure itself during processing is needed. For example, information concerning the final fibre length and orientation distribution functions, point-to-point fibre orientations, volume fractions, for a given aspect ratio are all significant in determining the resulting mechanical properties after processing. So far experiment has been most successful in providing data on the possible configurations the reinforcement may adopt [1,2]. Usually this is provided for relatively simple cross-sections and flow histories, which are used, with varying

degrees of success, to extrapolate to the behaviour in a real component. Such predictive modelling is essential for good design work since the cost of tooling even two or three prototype components may be prohibitively expensive.

A successful theoretical model of the resulting micro-structure of a flow processed composite, from which the mechanical properties may be readily determined (e.g. by finite element methods) has many obvious advantages. It can provide for much more creative design work, multiple conceptual testing and the possibility of manufacturing process evaluation. The problems in developing such a model lie, not so much in the prediction of mechanical properties from microstructure, but in determining the microstructure due to a particular flow history. One may define at least three areas of difficulty at present; (i) accurately modelling the flow behaviour of the polymer matrix (including time and temperature effects that are often non-linear), (ii) modelling the behaviour of the reinforcing fibres in the matrix and (iii) modelling the interaction between the two.

Models so far produced have concentrated on dilute suspensions of fibres in a flowing polymer model [3 -6]. In reality such suspensions would provide little or no reinforcement for the composite material. Here the emphasis is on establishing an accurate model for the polymer matrix itself. The principle problem, currently, seems to be the development of sufficiently fast, accurate finite element algorithms to model the well-characterised behaviour of the matrix. The volume fraction of reinforcement is assumed so low that there is no interaction between fibres.

The work to be described below starts with the contrary assumption that the matrix flow behaviour can be modelled reasonably accurately and, instead, concentrates on the physical consequences of having high volume fractions of fibres. Hence the most significant effect to be explored, and the consequences thereof, are multiple fibre-fibre interactions. From experimental observation [7,8] these are known to be capable of leading to extended regions of fibre orientation, or a random log-jam effect, depending on fibre length, packing fraction, flow history etc. It is just these effects that the model described below seeks to explore.

MODEL

The computer model developed is conveniently considered in two parts. Firstly, a programme which establishes, by various means, an initial, high volume fraction, fibre configuration. Parameters such as aspect ratio, fibre length distribution and orientation distribution etc. may be specified for this configuration. Secondly, a flow programme provides for the rotation and translation of individual fibres, whilst checking for interaction between fibres, to enable the development of new fibre configurations, as a result of a particular flow history.

In both programmes the interaction between fibres is a simple proximity check whereby no two fibres are allowed to overlap or pass through each other. The fibres are generated and moved within, typically, a cubic space of a fixed size of, say, 100 units cubed. The space shape must be orthorhombic but need not always be cubic. A typical fibre, of aspect ratio 20 say, may be 20 units long and 1 unit in diameter. The same aspect ratio can be produced using any particular combination of length and diameter in the same ratio. Hence by varying the absolute size of the fibre with respect to the box it is possible to examine boundary effects. The cube can either represent a physically enclosed space with solid sides or represent a repeating unit cell with periodic boundary conditions. In this case if part of a fibre emerges through a face of the cube, the emergent part of the fibre 'reappears' on the opposing face of the cube. A combination is possible in both programmes to simulate, for example, the existence of a solid boundary. The programme is not designed for a complete computer-aided-engineering approach to design, but could be adapted for use with such programmes. For example the modelled cube could represent the time development of one element of a finite element model for composite processing.

The procedure for packing fibres to obtain an initial configuration is, in many ways, the most difficult part of the programme. Various types of starting configuration can be provided which may bear varying resemblances to the real situation. Only after the flow procedure and comparison of initial and final configurations can one really have complete confidence in the validity of the start configuration. As an example, the most commonly used method of packing fibres is to place them randomly within the space available and to test each fibre as it is added, for overlap with adjacent fibres. If overlap does occur the fibre is

'thrown away' and another, randomly positioned and oriented, is inserted. The orientation of each fibre may be randomly or selectively chosen. The process is continued until the volume fraction has plateaued. Extensive tests have been required to ensure that sufficient attempts to insert fibres had occurred, in turn ensuring the volume fraction had truly plateaued. Such Monte-Carlo type calculations inevitably require large amounts of computing time. The result of such a procedure, for the case of in-plane random fibres, of a low aspect ratio is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Diagram of in-plane packing of fibres of aspect ratio 3:1 using a periodic boundary condition.

Alternative procedures, akin to pouring the fibres into the space are possible, here the region initially filled is restricted to one side of the cube and expanded slowly, as each region is filled in turn. However, although slightly higher packing fractions may be achievable by this technique, they are not necessarily appropriate to fibre flow problems, in that very high volume fraction random fibre arrays are completely intractable, allowing no freedom of movement for the individual fibres.

Having achieved a suitable initial configuration a flow field is imposed on the fibres in terms of a rotational and translational motion of each fibre about its centre of mass. In practice this is a short time step iterative process. The time step chosen must be such that the distance moved by any given fibre in one time step is of the order of one-two fibre diameters, to allow for the application of an overlap test with neighbouring fibres. One full unit of time is the equivalent to attempting to move each fibre in the configuration once.

A periodic boundary can also be used to follow the progressive effect of a given flow field on a specific element of the composite; in effect following it through the mould. In other words we use, effectively a Lagrangian rather than a Eulerian fluid flow formulation. It has the particular advantage, in this case, that the boundary conditions on the representative element can be altered as, for example, it passes from a region close to a boundary to the centre of a mould and away again. Thus a series of 'passes' can be used to build up a picture of a complex mould by following different time and spatial histories through it.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

So far work has concentrated on one of three specific initial configurations; completely random three-dimensional fibre arrays, in-plane random fibre arrays (ie 2-D random fibres) and restricted orientation (aligned) fibres. These results in themselves are of interest as it is possible to vary fibre length and orientation angle distributions etc. to see how each parameter alone effects the maximum achievable packing fraction. Analytical work [9] and idealised packing experiments [10] have been done on certain aspects of this problem, but a computer model such as this is potentially capable of a systematic survey of the appropriate parameters.

Figs. 2 and 3 illustrate some of the results so far obtained. In fig. 2 we show the variation in volume fraction for random and in-plane random fibres as a function of aspect ratio. In fig. 3 we illustrate (for the in-plane random case) the variation in volume fraction with restriction in orientation angle.

At the time of writing insufficient results are available to present any significant trends as a result of processing such initial

Figure 2. Volume fraction as a function of aspect ratio for random and in-plane random fibres.

configurations using the second programme previously described. It would seem to be the case that the maximum permissible volume fraction achievable, purely on space filling grounds, represents a configuration that is intractable to flow and that this itself is a function of the allowed fibre orientation angle. It is possible to envisage regions of differing orientation function and hence volume fraction co-existing, with the only possible means of recoalescing being fibre degradation. Experimentally there is certainly evidence for regions of local order [1], of quite extended size (fibre length) in even so-called random fibre configurations. Even in the results presented here, to a small extent in fig. 1, regions of ordering are apparent in the 2D randomly packed configurations, this effect and the effect it has on any subsequent flow is also under investigation, this includes the possibility of solid walls generating significant skin effects.

Figure 3. Volume fraction as a function of restriction of orientation angle for in-plane random fibres of aspect ratio = 12:1.

CONCLUSION

A model has been developed to examine high volume fraction short fibre composites. Each fibre of the model may represent a single fibre or a bundle of fibres in the real composite. The interaction between fibres at high volume fraction is the principal object of the study and the programme allows for any combination of fibre length and orientation distribution, both globally and from point-to-point. This has the added advantage (as yet not exploited) of being able to use the flow programme alone to examine the behaviour of an experimentally determined fibre distribution (e.g. by image analysis techniques).

It is felt that the currently available experimental descriptions for fibre configurations in flow processed composites, are inadequate for full comparison with the current model. For example it is not sufficient to provide the fibre length distribution or even the orientation angle distribution. Not only must these be provided for the total specimen (e.g. of an injection moulding) but also from point-to-point to determine fluctuations in the distributions. Only by such extremely tedious detailed observations will sufficient data be available to determine the time history of representative elements of the composite, as they pass through a given moulding operation.

Programmes such as these represent the only way of developing truly predictive design procedures for composite components. Although they involve considerable amounts of computing power, the current developments in work-station technology provide the possibility of using reasonably realistic models within the next few years.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors wish to acknowledge the receipt of an SERC research studentship and additional financial support from I.C.I. New Science Group, for M.D. Ferrar during the period of this work.

REFERENCES

1. Darlington, M.W., McGinley, P.L. and Smith, G.R., Structure and anisotropy of stiffness in glass fibre reinforced thermoplastics. J. Mater. Sci., 1976, 11, 877-86.
2. Folkes, M.J. and Russell, D.A.M., Orientation effects during the flow of short fibre reinforced themoplastics. Polymer, 1980, 21, 1252-58.
3. Givler, R.C., Crochet, M.J. and Pipes, R.B., Numerical prediction of fibre orientation in dilute suspensions. J. Composite Materials., 1983, 17, 330-43.
4. Lockett, F.J., Flow of polymer melts containing chopped fibres; Part 1: Internal Mechanics. National Physical Laboratory, Division of Materials Application, Report No. 25, Dec. 1972.
5. Salinas, A. and Pittman, J.F.T., Bending and breaking fibres in sheared suspensions. Poly. Eng. and Sci., 1981, 21, 23-31.
6. Dinh, S.M. and Armstrong, R.C., A rheological equation of state for semiconcentrated fibre suspensions. J. Rheol., 1984, 28, 207-27.

7. Folgar, F. and Tucker, C.L., Orientation behaviour of fibres in concentrated suspensions. J. Reinf. Plast. and Composites, 1984, 3, 98-119.
8. Pipes, R.B., McCullough, R.L. and Taggart, D.G., Behaviour of discontinuous fibre composites: fibre orientation. In Composite, Materials, Proc. Japan/U.S. Conference, Tokyo, 1981, 102-10.
9. Evans, K.E. and Gibson, A.G., Prediction of the maximum packing fraction achievable in randomly oriented short-fibre composites. Comp. Sci. and Tech., 1986, 25, 149-62.
10. Milewski, J.V., A study of the packing of milled fibreglass and glass beads. Composites, Nov. 1973, 258-65.